

DEEP LEARNING APPROACH TO FISH DETECTION AND TRACKING IN UNDERWATER VIDEO

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Abstract

Deep learning has become more common in recent years because it has achieved excellent results in accuracy in several areas. The importance of deep learning in knowing the localization, classification and tracking, based on the frame. In this proposed work, we will focus on the development of the system of fish recognition and track underwater, in order to solve the challenges facing the system such as fish behavior by determining the type of fish, track their trajectory and color can determine whether the fish is healthy or not. The most of the current methods depend on the identification of fish in tank and under restricted conditions, and use small datasets containing a small number of fish and fish species are limited, second most of these methods are used handcraft feature and the methods unsuitable for large datasets. In order to obtain the best recognition and detection of fish, we will develop a new approach based on the latest deep learning algorithms to develop the fish recognition system, track its trajectory and its interaction with the its neighbors of the fish. The proposed work presents the latest methods of deep learning in real-time object tracking, to improve the fish tracking system including detection, motion and interaction. Firstly, detection of the fish including localization, classification, and segmentation fish. In order to improve the accuracy of classification and localization. Our proposed work has three methods including detection, motion, interaction.

The detection has three steps. Firstly, the fish video enhancement using image processing. Secondly, we improve the algorithm by convolution neural network (CNN) to detection the fish, locate the object of fish through region Proposal Network (RPN). In the segmentation method, we develop semantic segmentation, in order to get the best boundaries for the image fish. Then compare the target fish with the detection fish. Third, we develop Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) and Long Short-Term Memories (LSTM) for motion the fish and know its speed then identify the detection fish trajectory through the target fish trajectory. Finally, we develop RNN and LSTM for interaction, the fish and know its interaction of the target fish with its neighbours, then identify the detection fish trajectory through the target fish. Then determine the status of the fish.

1 INTRODUCTION

Deep learning has had a great impact in recent years because of its effectiveness in many fields such as computer vision [1], image recognition [2]. a deep learning is the branch of machine learning, The Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is the most effective of deep learning, in recognition and detected item in the frame. Multi-object tracking was achieved through deep learning because it achieved high accuracy results compared to other tracking algorithms. However, most of the research was on pedestrians while much of the work was not done to track animals such as fish. Tracking fish is a

major challenge because fish swim in different directions and at different speeds. Fish tracking, identification and interaction with their fish neighbors in the same group may be a major challenge.

CNN was characterized by a high accuracy of recognition of the object within the images compared to other algorithms based on conventional computer vision techniques such as AlexNet network [2] has achieved excellent results using the CNN in detection, recognition, and classification of the object from the images. LSTM and RNN do get a better job at each time for capturing based on overtime for their many gates. The LSTM have proven effective in many areas such as language translation, and image and video annotation [3].

2 PROPOSED WORK

The proposed work mainly consists of five phases as shown in Figure 1. 1st stage: Preprocessing is enhancement rate detection and recognition of fish video underwater to reduce external factors and get frames by using image processing method.

2nd stage: Multi-object detection enhancement recognition methods based on deep learning approach through enhancement CNN, RPN and semantic segmentation to classification and localization for each frame and combined between methods.

3rd stage: Multi-object tracking enhancement deep learning approach for object tracking by combing of Recurrent neural network (RNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) methods to propose tracking methods that include interaction and motion between fish with each other.

4th stage: Training and evaluation an improved framework for automated fish detection and tracking in underwater video, by the training tracking methods and proposed RNN and the fully connected layer to determine the amount of similarity score between the target fish and detection fish then evaluation tracking methods.

5th stage: To design a better-automated framework for tracking multiple fish movement and recognition in underwater videos

Finally: To evaluation and design a better-automated framework for tracking multiple fish movement and recognition in underwater videos which include incorporating the above enhanced methods in the enhanced framework.

Figure 1: Overview of the proposed fish tracking system.

References

- [1] Simonyan.Karen , Zisserman .Andrew, 2014,," Two-stream convolutional networks for action recognition in videos". In NIPS, pp. 568–576.
- [2] Krizhevsky. A, Sutskever. I, E.Hinton. G,2012,," Image net classification with deep convolutional neural networks", in: Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems, StatelineNV, USA,2012, pp.1097–1105.
- [3] Sutskever. I, Vinyals. O, and V. Le. Q, 2014,"Sequence to sequence learning with neural networks," in Advances in neural information processing systems, pp. 3104-3112.